

TEACHERS' TEACHING PERFORMANCE IN ACADEMIC CULTURES REVIEW: IMPLICATION FOR PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

Teacher teaching performance is a crucial factor determining the quality of education and student learning outcomes. Current discourse emphasizes the role of academic culture in shaping teacher instructional effectiveness, but empirical studies linking these two constructs are limited. This study aims to analyze the influence of academic culture on teacher teaching performance and explore its implications for professional development initiatives. Using a mixed-methods approach, this study integrates quantitative data from a survey of 91 respondents and interviews with five elementary school teachers in West Jakarta, Indonesia. The quantitative analysis indicates a positive relationship between academic culture and teaching performance, with a correlation coefficient of 0.368. The t-test result is 7.199, which is greater than the t-table (1.662), indicating statistical significance. Qualitative findings indicate that supportive academic cultures, such as (1) collaboration and sharing of good practices, (2) reflective learning and self-evaluation, (3) development of new skills and (4) innovation and creativity in learning, thus strengthening academic culture can be an effective strategy in their professional development programs. Integration of cultural dimensions into teacher training, culture-based professional development strategies, and institutional policies such as academic norms, mentoring, and peer collaboration, is highly recommended.

Keywords: teachers' teaching performance, academic cultures, professional development.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the current education system, the quality of educational services depends heavily on the bottom-line performance of teachers how they plan, implement, evaluate, and facilitate student development (Guo, 2024). However, although teachers are often considered the primary determinant of success, many schools report that their teaching performance is suboptimal. For example, in the context of new curricula or changes in education policies, teachers often struggle to adapt their teaching practices to meet contextual demands and student needs (Gemink et al., 2021; Sigalla & Kimario, 2025). Furthermore, teacher performance assessments and evaluations of teaching practices are not always conducted consistently, systematically, and comprehensively. Several studies have shown that existing assessment instruments sometimes only evaluate administrative aspects or outputs, while neglecting pedagogical aspects, professionalism, reflection, and continuous development (Botuzova et al., 2023; Fernández-Sánchez et al., 2025). This results in a lack of constructive feedback and limited opportunities for teacher professional development.

Within different academic cultures, such as local norms, values, structures, and demands, what is considered "good performance" by national policies or standards may not align with the realities of school culture and teachers' daily experiences. This misalignment creates problems, making performance improvement through training or evaluation irrelevant or even unsuccessful if it does not take local academic culture and context into account. A large body of empirical literature and literature reviews demonstrate that professional development and professional learning communities have a significant impact on teacher performance (Çopur & Demirel, 2022; Pan & Cheng, 2023). Recent research reports that all dimensions of professional learning (shared values and vision, supportive leadership, supportive conditions, collective learning and application, and shared personal practice) have a positive correlation with teacher performance (Mydin et al., 2024).

Studies also show that professional development programs that are carried out continuously, contextually, and relevant to instructional needs can improve teachers' teaching practices in the classroom (Dhungana et al., 2021). The study found students were accompanied by coaching, content-focused training, and collaborative structures were more effective in improving teaching practices and student learning outcomes (Correnti et al., 2021; Gore & Rosser, 2022). A combined review of many large-scale studies also showed that teacher professional development was positively related to instructional practices and student achievement, although the authors of the meta-analysis cautioned that only a small number of studies were methodologically robust enough to demonstrate causality (Lindvall et al., 2025).

Furthermore, aspects of academic culture have been shown to influence the implementation of student outcomes. In the school context, such as shared values, collaborative culture, and leadership support, academic culture helps determine whether teacher professional learning can be implemented effectively (McChesney & Cross, 2023). Other research shows that teaching performance assessment, when integrated into preservice teacher education, can trigger professional culture change and improve the quality of teacher preparation for classroom practice (Adie & Wyatt-Smith, 2021). All these

findings underpin the understanding that teacher performance is not only an individual outcome, but also a product of the interaction between pengembangan, assessment, and academic culture.

Although numerous studies confirm the influence of school academic culture on teacher performance, few studies have holistically examined how "academic culture" (including norms, values, institutional structures, leadership, and collaboration) broadly impacts teaching performance. Most studies examine only one aspect (e.g., PD alone, PLCs, or performance assessments), without integrating all three aspects into a single analytical framework. This study explores the practical implications for teacher professional development based on a comprehensive review of academic culture.

Academically, the researchers expand the literature on the relationship between school academic culture and teacher teaching practices. Practically, the results of this study provide a reference for policymakers and teacher training providers to design professional development strategies that are appropriate to the context of academic culture in schools. Therefore, the purpose of this study to analyze the influence of academic culture on teacher teaching performance and explore its implications for their professional development initiatives.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Teaching Performance

Teacher teaching performance is often viewed as a key factor determining the success of the learning process and student learning outcomes. In international literature, teacher effectiveness, encompassing teaching performance, is identified as a key source in determining students' academic and socioeconomic futures. Although defining the characteristics of effective teachers remains a challenge (Burroughs et al., 2019). Factors commonly used as indicators of teacher effectiveness include teaching experience, professional knowledge (subject knowledge and pedagogical knowledge), and learning opportunities, such as teaching duration and material coverage (König et al., 2022).

Recent research also shows that teacher psychological aspects, particularly teacher self-efficacy, play a significant role in student academic outcomes. A meta-analysis covering 71 studies and more than 250,000 teachers showed a positive correlation between teacher self-efficacy and student academic performance (Ma et al., 2025). Thus, teacher professional development involves not only cognitive or methodological aspects, but also teachers' self-confidence and belief in their abilities (Leijen et al., 2022; Wong et al., 2023).

However, the literature also shows traditional approaches to measuring teaching performance, which focus on inputs such as educational background or length of teaching experience, have limitations (Ghaffarian Asl & Osam, 2021; Javornik & Klemenčič Mirazchiyski, 2023). Historically, teacher evaluation methods can be divided into three categories: input, process (the teaching process), and outcome (student learning outcomes). Numerous studies have shown that outcome-based measurement (student outcomes, value added) and observation of the learning process are more valid in assessing teacher effectiveness than mere input (Brooks & Springer, 2021). Emerging paradigms, such as Teaching Effectiveness Research (TER), emphasize the importance of combining various evaluation methods to capture the complexity of teaching practice, including classroom interactions, social contexts, and teacher-student dynamics (Vieluf & Klieme, 2023).

2.2 Academic Culture

The concept of academic culture has attracted the attention of numerous studies in higher education, although its definition is not yet standardized and universal (Pedraja-Rejas et al., 2022). A recent systematic scoping review revealed that of the 961 literature reviewed, only 94 met the inclusion criteria, and only 23 explicitly defined academic culture and its structural components (Tikhonova et al., 2023). Academic culture reflects the collective mindset, norms, ethics, and behaviors formed within the academic environment, including among faculty, students, and the institution (Peyravinejad et al., 2025; Whittaker & Montgomery, 2022). Academic culture comprises aspects such as academic outlook, academic spirit, academic ethics, and the academic environment.

Developing an academic culture requires a well-planned strategy (Allumi et al., 2024). Empirical studies in educational institutions show leadership support, institutional policies, and the active involvement of lecturers and students in academic activities such as research, publications, and scientific discussions are supporting factors for the successful development of an academic culture (Kienast, 2023; Owan et al., 2024; Rojak, 2023). For example, research on strategies for developing a student academic culture demonstrates the importance of funding for scientific activities, academic writing training, student scientific communities, and academic networks with foreign universities. Furthermore, the diversity of social, cultural, organizational, and historical contexts of institutions can lead to differing interpretations of academic culture from one university to another (Lozano, 2023; Torres, 2022).

Thus, academic culture can be understood as a multidimensional construct encompassing values, ethics, norms, behaviors, the environment, and academic practices within educational institutions. Understanding and developing academic culture requires a reflective and contextual approach tailored to the characteristics of the institution, its members, and its educational goals.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

This study employed mixed methods to obtain a comprehensive overview of the topic. This approach combined quantitative and qualitative data, allowing for in-depth analysis and triangulation of findings. The sample consisted of 91 elementary school teachers in West Jakarta, selected using purposive sampling to ensure the representation of teachers who were actively involved in academic activities and had at least two years of teaching experience. Furthermore, the

study involved in-depth interviews with five selected teachers, chosen based on their teaching experience and involvement in the school's academic culture, to gain a more detailed qualitative perspective on teaching practices and school dynamics. Quantitative data were collected through a questionnaire, tested for validity and reliability, containing indicators of academic culture (such as professional collaboration, pedagogical innovation, and institutional support) and teacher teaching performance (including planning, implementation, and evaluation of learning). Qualitative data were obtained through semi-structured interviews, in which teachers were asked to describe their experiences in implementing teaching practices, their perceptions of academic support, and the challenges they faced in improving their professional competence. Quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS version 25 to examine the relationship between academic culture and teaching performance. For qualitative data, thematic analysis was used, where interview transcripts were coded to identify key themes, patterns, and contexts that support the interpretation of the findings.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Normality Test

The calculation results obtained a calculated L-value of 0.086. This value is smaller than the L-table value ($n = 91$ and $\alpha = 0.05$) of 0.091, so that the calculated L-value \leq L-table is obtained, so it can be concluded that the distribution of academic culture data on teacher teaching performance is normally distributed.

4.2 Homogeneity Test

The results of the calculation of the homogeneity test of academic culture on teacher teaching performance yielded an F-value of 0.555. The F-value with $df = 90$ ($n-1 = 91-1$) at $\alpha = 0.05$ was 0.706. Therefore, it can be said that F-value \leq F-value. This indicates that the data set is homogeneous.

4.3 Significance and Linearity

The results of the test of teacher teaching performance on academic culture yielded a constant (a) of 87.285 and a regression coefficient (b) of 0.446. Thus, the regression equation is $\hat{Y} = 87.285 + 0.446X$. The results of the significance and linearity tests can be seen in the following ANOVA table:

Table 1. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Significance and Linearity Test

Source of Variation	Degrees of Freedom	Sum of Squares	Mean Sum of Squares	F-count	F-table $\alpha = 0,05$
Total	91	10106.681			
Coefficient (a)	1				
Regression	1	3719.489	3719.489	51.828	3.10
Residual	89	6387.192	71.766		
Good fit	42	3252.726	77.446	1.161	1.641
Error	47	3134.467	66.691		

Based on Table 1 above, the significance test of the regression of academic culture on teacher teaching performance yielded a calculated F of 51.828. This value is greater than the F-table value at $\alpha = 0.05$ of 3.10, thus declaring the regression equation significant. The linearity test also yielded a calculated F of 1.161, while the Ftable value at an error level of α (0.05) with a degree of freedom in the numerator of 42 and a dk in the denominator of 47 was 1.641. Since the calculated F-value \leq F-table, the regression equation for academic culture on teacher teaching performance is linear.

4.4 The Effect of Academic Cuulture (X) to Teachers' Teaching Performance (Y)

The coefficient calculations revealed an effect of variable X on variable Y of $p_y = 0.368$, $\text{sig.} = 0.000 < 0.05$, while the calculated t value was 7.199, while the ttable value at a significance level of α (0.05) was 1.662 for $dk = (91-2 = 89)$. Because $t\text{-test} > t\text{-table}$, H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. Therefore, it can be concluded that academic culture has a significant influence on teacher teaching performance in elementary schools. (See Table 2)

Table 2. Coefficient of Influence of X on Y

Influence Variable	Coefficient	t-test	Sig.	t-table
				$\alpha = 0,05$
X on Y	0,368	7,199	0,000	1,662

4.5 Teachers' Professional Development Through Academic Culture

Academic culture serves as a primary foundation for teacher professional development, as it provides opportunities for learning and collaboration, fostering reflection, creativity, and innovation that directly impact teaching performance.

Table 3. Teachers' Professional Development Through Academic Culture

No	Respondents	Question 1: How does the academic culture at your school support your professional development?	Question 2: Examples of professional development activities you have participated in?	Question 3: How does academic culture impact your teaching performance?
1	Teacher A	Teachers feel the academic culture encourages collaboration between teachers and reflective learning.	Digital literacy workshops and active learning methods training.	Increased creativity in designing new learning methods.
2	Teacher B	The academic culture emphasizes classroom action research and regular evaluation.	Project-based lesson planning training and teacher-to-teacher observations.	Facilitated the adaptation of more innovative learning methods.
3	Teacher C	The school provides dedicated time for scholarly discussions and the sharing of best practices.	Weekly discussions with senior teachers and internal seminars.	Increased confidence in dealing with varying student abilities.
4	Teacher D	Teachers are encouraged to continuously learn and apply new knowledge in the classroom.	International online training and collaborative learning.	Improved ability to integrate technology into learning.
5	Teacher E	The academic culture encourages regular self-evaluation and reflection on learning.	Classroom management and peer review workshops.	Helped improve classroom management and student interaction.

The interview results in Table 3 indicate that the academic culture in schools has a positive influence on teacher professional development. Teacher A revealed that the academic culture encourages collaboration between teachers and reflective learning practices, allowing them to participate in digital literacy workshops and training in active learning methods. Teacher B emphasized the academic culture's emphasis on classroom action research and regular evaluation, which led to her active participation in project-based lesson planning training and teacher-to-teacher observations. Teacher C highlighted the availability of dedicated time for scientific discussions and the sharing of good practices, such as weekly discussions with senior teachers and internal seminars, although motivation sometimes waned during high workloads. Teacher D stated that there needs to be encouragement to continuously learn and apply new knowledge through international training and collaborative learning, although technical support for technology is still lacking. Teacher E observed that the academic culture encourages regular self-evaluation and reflection, followed by classroom management workshops and peer review, although some training materials are not fully relevant to the curriculum. The explanations above imply that the academic culture contributes to improving teacher teaching performance, particularly in terms of creativity, innovative learning methods, confidence in addressing differences in student abilities, technology integration, and classroom management and interaction with students. Consistently strengthening the academic culture and providing adequate infrastructure support are key to successful teacher professional development. Thus, teacher professional development through academic culture can be implemented through: (1) collaboration and sharing of good practices, (2) reflective learning and self-evaluation, (3) development of new skills and (4) innovation and creativity in learning.

5. DISCUSSION

The results of the study indicate that academic culture has a significant influence on the teaching performance of elementary school teachers, with an influence coefficient of $\rho = 0.368$ and a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This finding is supported by the calculated t-value of $7.199 > t$ -table of 1.662, thus accepting the alternative hypothesis, indicating that the stronger the academic culture in a school, the better the teacher's teaching performance. Practically, this coefficient value indicates that academic culture contributes to improving the quality of lesson planning, instructional strategies, and teacher evaluation.

These results align with the view that academic culture serves as a foundation for shaping teachers' professional behavior. Okure (2023) asserts that academic culture provides a set of values, norms, and intellectual practices that influence teaching quality. In the elementary school context, values such as collaboration, openness to innovation, and support for scholarly activity encourage teachers to improve their pedagogical quality. This is consistent with the findings of

Theoharis (2024), that school environments with a strong academic culture can enhance teacher commitment and instructional competence.

Furthermore, research by Li & Khairani (2025) shows a structured and supportive academic culture strengthens teachers' professional identity, ultimately increasing their self-efficacy in managing learning. Similarly, a study by de Jong et al. (2021) revealed an academic culture developed through professional learning communities positively impacts the quality of teachers' instruction by providing a space for collaboration, reflection, and the exchange of best practices.

From a professional development perspective, academic culture not only shapes teachers' mindsets but also creates an ecosystem that enables collective learning. Jessiman et al. (2022) emphasize institutions with expansive academic cultures are able to encourage teachers to engage in ongoing capacity-building activities. This is relevant to research findings showing that teachers in strong academic environments tend to have better teaching performance due to the structural and social support they receive during the learning process.

Thus, these research findings reinforce the premise that academic culture is a key factor in developing teacher teaching performance, particularly at the elementary education level. Strengthening academic culture should focus on developing professional learning communities, supporting instructional leadership, and creating a school environment that promotes collaboration, innovation, and continuous learning.

6. CONCLUSION

This study concludes that academic culture has a significant influence on the teaching performance of elementary school teachers. The stronger the academic culture in a school, the better the quality of teachers' teaching performance, particularly in aspects of creativity, learning innovation, the use of active methods, classroom management, and the ability to integrate technology. Interview results also show that academic culture is an important foundation for teacher professional development through collaboration, reflection, new skill development, classroom action research, scientific discussions, and internal and external training. This means that academic culture has been proven to play a role in creating a work environment that is conducive to the continuous growth of teachers' pedagogical and professional competencies. This study has several limitations that need to be considered. It did not explore intermediary variables such as instructional leadership, teacher motivation, or the quality of the work environment that could potentially strengthen or weaken the influence of academic culture on teacher teaching performance. In addition, several respondents mentioned obstacles such as workload, lack of technical support, and irrelevant training materials, but these factors have not been explored further. Therefore, it is recommended that schools strengthen academic culture through the development of professional learning communities, providing collaborative spaces, and supporting learning innovation. Further research needs to involve larger samples, develop structural models that include moderator or mediator variables, and conduct longitudinal studies to examine the impact of academic culture on teacher performance in the long term.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS/SUGGESTIONS

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations are proposed to enhance teachers' teaching performance through the strengthening of academic culture and the development of effective professional development programs. First, educational institutions should intentionally foster a supportive academic culture that promotes collaboration and the sharing of good teaching practices among teachers. Structured forums such as professional learning communities, lesson study groups and peer discussions can facilitate continuous knowledge exchange and collective problem-solving which are proven to positively influence teaching performance. Second, professional development programs should integrate reflective learning and self-evaluation as core components. Teachers need regular opportunities to reflect on their instructional practices, receive constructive feedback and engage in evidence-based self-improvement. This can be achieved through mentoring systems, reflective journals, classroom observations and feedback-oriented supervision.

Third, training programs should focus on the continuous development of new pedagogical, technological and instructional skills. Given the dynamic nature of educational demands, professional development initiatives should be adaptive, needs-based and aligned with contemporary teaching challenges, including digital literacy, student-centered learning and innovative instructional strategies. Fourth, school leaders and policymakers are encouraged to create institutional policies that support innovation and creativity in teaching. This includes providing academic freedom, resources and incentives for teachers to experiment with innovative learning approaches without fear of failure. A culture that values experimentation and creativity can significantly enhance teacher motivation and instructional quality. Finally, policymakers at the district and national levels should incorporate academic culture as a strategic dimension in teacher professional development frameworks. By embedding cultural values such as collaboration, reflection and innovation into professional standards and training policies, professional development initiatives can become more sustainable and impactful in improving teachers' teaching performance.

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